

EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT OF NOBLE MORAL VALUES IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH SCOUTING EXTRACULICULAR ACTIVITIES

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Abstract

Character education is an important aspect in student development in the modern era. Education of noble moral values plays a very important role in forming good character in students. Elementary school (SD) One effective approach in developing student character is through extracurricular activities. The general aim of this research is to describe and analyze the educational management of noble moral values for elementary school students through Scout extracurricular activities at Ma'arif NU Bojongjati Elementary School and Meraih Bintang Elementary School. This research uses a qualitative approach with the aim of exploring phenomena experienced by research subjects, such as behavior, perceptions, interests, motivations or actions, through words and language. The method used is a descriptive method. The results of the research show that noble moral education in elementary school through Scout extracurricular activities has special characteristics. First, the planning considers the noble moral values that you want to instill in students, such as honesty, discipline, a sense of responsibility and social awareness. Second, the chosen teaching method integrates these values through field activities, games and group discussions. Third, the aim of planning is to form positive character in students which is manifested in daily attitudes and behavior

Keywords: Management, Noble Moral Values, Scout Extracurricular

A. INTRODUCTION

Character education is an important aspect in student development in the modern era. Education of noble moral values plays a very important role in forming good character in students. Elementary school (SD) is the initial stage of formal education where students can begin to build strong character foundations. Therefore, it is important for schools to integrate education of noble moral values in their educational programs.

One effective approach in developing student character is through extracurricular activities. Extracurricular activities provide students with opportunities to develop their social, leadership, and responsibility skills outside of the classroom environment. Scouting is a popular extracurricular activity and has proven effective in educating students about the values of honesty, discipline, cooperation and responsibility.

However, in managing the education of students' noble moral values through Scout extracurricular activities, effective management is needed. Good educational management will ensure that educational goals and values are well integrated in the implementation of Scout extracurricular activities at school. It is in this context that this research was conducted to explore and describe the educational management of noble moral values for elementary school students through Scout extracurricular activities.

This research was conducted in two different elementary schools, namely Ma'arif NU Bojongjati Elementary School and Meraih Bintang Elementary School. These two schools were chosen because they have active Scout extracurricular programs and are dedicated to developing student character. By conducting a descriptive study at these two schools, this research aims to explain how the education management of students' noble moral values is carried out through Scout extracurricular activities at Ma'arif NU Bojongjati Elementary School and Meraih Bintang Elementary School.

With this research proposal, it is hoped that it can provide an overview of the effectiveness of educational management of students' noble moral values through Scout extracurricular activities in elementary school. It is hoped that the findings and recommendations of this research can become a reference for other schools in improving the educational management of students' noble moral values through extracurricular activities. To find out the description of the educational management of students' noble moral values through scout extracurricular activities at Ma'arif NU Bojongjati Elementary School and Meraih Bintang Pangandaran Elementary School, the researcher raised the title: "Educational Management of Noble Moral Values for Elementary School Students through Scout Extracurricular Activities (Descriptive Study in SD Ma'arif NU Bojongjati and SD Meraih Bintang)". The general aim of this research is to describe the educational management of noble moral values for elementary school students through Scout extracurricular activities at Ma'arif NU Bojongjati Elementary School and Meraih Bintang Elementary School.

The specific objectives of this research are to:

- a) Analyze the policies and plans carried out by the school in integrating the education of students' noble moral values through Scout extracurricular activities.
- b) Identifying the process of implementing Scout extracurricular activities as a means of educating students' noble moral values in the two elementary schools studied.
- c) Evaluate the role of teachers and administrators of Scout extracurricular activities in managing the education of students' noble moral values in the two elementary schools.
- d) Assess the impact and effectiveness of Scout extracurricular activities in shaping student character and developing noble moral values.
- e) Formulate recommendations for the two elementary schools studied to improve educational management of students' noble moral values through Scout extracurricular activities.

B. RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a qualitative approach with the aim of exploring phenomena experienced by research subjects, such as behavior, perceptions, interests, motivations or actions, through words and language. The method used is the descriptive method, which is an approach that helps researchers to explore and describe the situation being studied in a comprehensive, in-depth and extensive manner. With this qualitative approach and descriptive method, this research will provide an in-depth understanding of the conditions being studied.

Using descriptive methods, this research will describe in detail the policies, planning, implementation, role of teachers, and the impact of Scout extracurricular activities in shaping student character and developing noble moral values. This research will provide in-depth insight into the practices and experiences in both elementary schools, so that it can provide a better understanding of the educational management of students' noble moral values through Scout extracurricular activities at the elementary level.

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Planning for noble moral education in elementary school in extra scouting

The results of the research show that planning for noble moral education in elementary school through Scout extracurricular activities has special characteristics. First, the planning considers the noble moral values that you want to instill in students, such as honesty, discipline, a sense of responsibility and social awareness. Second, the chosen teaching method integrates these values through field activities, games and group discussions. Third, the aim of planning is to form positive character in students which is manifested in daily attitudes and behavior.

In the context of planning noble moral education, effective coordination is needed between Scout teachers, extracurricular committees, and the school to ensure that activity plans are in accordance with the school's educational vision and mission. Apart from that, inclusive planning also involves student participation in preparing the goals and agenda for Scout activities, so that they feel they have ownership and are actively involved in the process of educating noble moral values.

2. Organizing extra noble moral values for scouts

The research results show that organizing noble moral values in Scout extracurricular activities has several key aspects. First, organizing Scout activities promotes values such as honesty, teamwork, responsibility and discipline. Second, the Scout organizational structure is designed to facilitate the understanding and application of these values in the context of field activities, camps and social activities. Organizing noble moral values involves the important role of Scout teachers and extracurricular leaders in guiding students to understand and apply the values -values in various situations. The reward and recognition system is also used to encourage students to practice and maintain noble moral values in everyday life.

In organizing noble moral values, it is important to ensure students' active involvement and participation, so that they can better internalize these values. Apart from that, synergy between Scout teachers, students and the school is the main key in creating an educational environment that combines learning of noble moral values with Scout activities.

3. Implementation of elementary school students' values in extra scouting

The research results show that the implementation of student values in Scout extracurricular activities involves a number of important aspects. First, students are directed to apply noble moral values such as honesty, a sense of responsibility, cooperation and discipline through social interactions, group assignments and roles in the front group. Second, the implementation of these values is supported by teaching methods that involve situation simulations, games and group discussions.

Scout activities provide a good platform for elementary school students to hone and apply noble moral values in real situations. This is realized through participation in field activities, trips, and camping experiences that enable students to practice noble moral values in the context of everyday life.

It is important to note that the mentoring and guidance of Scout teachers greatly influences the level of success in implementing students' values. Scout teachers have an important role in guiding, providing feedback, and providing direction to students to apply these values correctly.

4. Educational supervision of extra scout elementary school students' grades

The research results show that monitoring students' values education in Scout extracurricular activities involves a number of key steps and aspects. First, supervision is carried out by Scout teachers who have a role in monitoring and evaluating the implementation of noble moral values by students during Scout activities. Second, supervision involves a continuous evaluation process to ensure that the desired values are truly reflected in student attitudes and behavior.

Parental involvement is also an integral part of monitoring student values education in Scout extracurriculars. Parents play an important role in supporting and monitoring their children's moral and character development outside the school environment.

It is important to note that educating students in values in scouting activities requires comprehensive involvement from teachers, school staff, and parents to ensure effective supervision. With good supervision, education on noble moral values can be implemented optimally, forming better student character

D. CONCLUSION

This research has focused on the educational management of noble moral values for elementary school students through extracurricular Scout activities at Ma'arif NU Elementary School Bojongjati and Meraih Bintang Elementary School. Based on the research results, it can be concluded that education of noble moral values through Scout activities has a significant role in shaping students' positive character. Management and implementation of noble moral values education requires good planning, effective organization, integrated implementation, and continuous supervision.

- 1) Directed Planning: It is recommended for schools and Scout teachers to develop a noble moral education plan that is directed and integrated with the school's vision and mission, paying attention to students' needs and potential.
- 2) Developing Learning Methods: Scout teachers should continue to develop innovative and interesting learning methods so that students can more easily understand and apply noble moral values.
- 3) Empowerment of Scout Teachers: Regular training and workshops are needed for Scout teachers to update their knowledge and skills in facilitating education in noble moral values.
- 4) Parent Participation: Involving parents in supporting and supervising the education of noble moral values at home is also important, so that character education becomes integrated both at school and in the family environment.
- 5) Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation: It is recommended to carry out routine monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of noble moral values education in Scout extracurriculars to ensure that educational goals are achieved optimally and make improvements as needed.

Inter-School Cooperation: It would be better if SD Ma'arif NU Bojongjati and SD Meraih Bintang collaborate and share the best experiences in implementing noble moral values education through Scout activities to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of the program.

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